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Report

ESTONIA

Migration and demographic patterns in Central-Eastern Europe

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Report

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Contents

5	Abstract
6	1. Introduction
10	2. Methodology, Definitions and Sources
11	3. Estonian diaspora
15	4. Immigrant stocks in Estonia
21	5. Immigrant flows in Estonia
25	6. Migration narrative scenario for Estonia
25	6.1 Factors influencing the situation of immigrants in Estonia
26	6.2 Migration prospect
29	7. Conclusions: Covid-19 pandemic: possible effects on immigration
30	References

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Abstract

This report is a part of deliverable “D.6.2. Report on migration and demographic patterns in the EU CEE countries and potential source countries” from the project FUME – Future Migration Scenarios for Europe (870649), financed with the Horizon 2020 programme. In particular, this country report focuses on critical analysis of immigration data from Estonia. The analysis consists of an overview of stock and flow data on migrants including such dimensions as age groups, gender, country of origin, education levels and length of residence. This report is a first step in an analytical exercise which aims to determine migration potential from and to Estonia and furthermore, to provide necessary data input for fine-tuning of the FUME migration projection model.

This report presents the historical framework of this transformation, major national groups of immigrants and their demographic structure. It also provides critical analysis on the validity of various statistical sources of data and draws some initial conclusions on the temporality/permanent nature of immigrants in Estonia.

Estonia, as other Baltic states shares some similar patterns of migration due to common history, including Russian and Soviet political dominance, political oppression during the communist times and settlement policies within the USRR. Nevertheless, its migration history resembles more Latvian than Lithuanian case. This is due to a relatively large Russian-speaking population which is still perceived as a problematic issue when it comes to assimilation and integration policies. Consequently, the historical experiences influence contemporary migration and integration policies: Estonia has a very selective and rather restrictive immigration policy, while the naturalization regulations are among the strictest ones in the EU.

1. Introduction

Estonia, as other Baltic states: Lithuania and Latvia shares some similar patterns. All of these countries have very small populations: 1.33 million in Estonia, 1.893 million in Latvia and 2.795 in Lithuania (data for 2021, Eurostat, 2021). This factor, connected with relative small area (Estonia - 43,432 km², Latvia - 64,589 km² and Lithuania - 65,300 km²), complicated historical ties with a neighbour with imperial traditions and aspirations (Russia) influences greatly contemporary migration and integration policies in these countries.

Estonia for centuries has been dominated by foreign powers: first by Livonian Order (German-originated military order who organized crusade to Christianise Livonia in 13th century (contemporary Latvia and South Estonia), then followed by Swedish and Polish occupation (mid 16-early 18th century) and finally by incorporation into Russian Empire (1710-1918). Ethnic national identity started to take visible shape in only 1850s which, after Estonian War of Independence (1918-1920) was finally acknowledge by Soviet Union who recognized independent state of Estonia.

When it comes to migration history, the first foreign settlers in these territories were German merchants, craftsmen and farmers, who arrived to Estonia in Medieval times. As for emigration, Estonians started to move under the Russian occupation: in the first half of 19th century around 3-4% of the Estonian population lived outside the traditional homeland, but in its close geographical proximity: Sant Petersburg, Pskov, Vitebsk and Southern Livonia. Of course, as many other ethnic and national minorities in Russian Empire, some of the Estonians have been also sent into exile in Siberia (Kulu & Tammaru, 2000). With the industrialization period and increased economic growth in Europe, also the population movements intensified. Many Estonians left their homeland, seeking better life opportunities in other Russian provinces. This was mostly agrarian emigration, as the pool of arable land in Estonia was limited. Therefore, starting from the second half of 19th century up to the beginning of 20th century, Estonians created rural settlements in Northwest Russia, the Volga region, the Crimea, the Caucasus and Siberia. According to most popular estimates, around 200 thousand people left Estonia in this period (Kulu, 2003).

Estonians had also participated in transatlantic system of migration, moving overseas in late 19th and early 20th century, but this emigration was relatively small in numbers. As the results some of Estonian settlements have been created in South and North Dakota, Wisconsin and Montana in the US, and in the Alberta province in Canada. The total population of Estonians in Northern America as for 1920 was estimated at 10 thousand (Kulu & Tammaru, 2000).

The interwar period (1918-1939) was a period of political, but also economic instability in Estonia. Consequently, out-migration from the country had intensified: in 1920-1930s additional 15 thousand Estonians left their homeland to North and South America and Australia. In total, at the end of 1930s, the Estonian diaspora consisted of ca. 175-180 thousand persons living abroad, out of which the largest group was in Soviet Union (143 thousand, Ibid).

During World War II, the migration of Estonians has intensified, but – as in the case of the entire region – it was mostly politically-driven. Between 1939 and 1944 some 70 thousand Estonians have left for Sweden and Germany as political refugees, then resettling to other countries in the

West – including the US, Canada, Australia and the UK. After the end of the war, many of them decided to stay in the West rather than returning to communist Estonia. It is estimated that around 85-90 thousand Estonians lived in the Western countries at the beginning of 1950s: they were mostly political refugees who did not acknowledge the annexation of Estonia by Soviet Union and remained loyal to Estonian government-in-exile.

Soviet Union has annexed Estonia as Estonian Soviet Socialist Republic already in 1940, and soon the political oppression towards non-communist opposition started. Around 11 thousand of Estonians have been deported to Siberia to Gulags in 1941, and then another 20 thousand in 1949. The Soviets started the policy of Russification, and massive settlement of Russian-speaking population into the republic, a process which in the West was labelled as colonization (Annus, 2012). The settled Russian-speaking elite was supposed to represent the interest of Moscow and their number was planned to surpass the indigenous ethnic Estonian population (Hughes, 2005). Moreover, even as the economic development under a communist rule is assessed in a mixed way (with contemporary critique of collectivization of farms and rapid industrialization which had negative ecologic effects), the Estonian republic in post-war period has witnessed rapid industrialization and increased investments (Klesment, 2009). As the consequence, Estonian Socialist Soviet Republic was one of the most developed parts of Soviet economy, with relatively high standards of living. For instance, in 1986 the living space in households per capita was 34.9% larger than average in Soviet Union, while the infant mortality was 37% lower than the average. Estonia also ranked first among the Soviet republics in the number of private cars per 1000 population (Park, 1994).

Therefore, many Russian-speaking persons from other republics – although encouraged by communist government – settled voluntarily, attracted by better life conditions. In the period of 1945-1989 the number of Russian-speaking population has risen from 26 thousand to 602 thousand, and a share of Estonians in the Republic has fallen from 97% of the population to 62% in the same timeframe (Saar et al., 2017). Finally, some of ethnic Estonians who lived in other parts of USSR decided to return to Estonia: for years 1945-1989 their number was estimated at 52-54 thousand (Kulu & Tammaru, 2000).

Moreover, most of Russian-speaking migrants who came to Estonia during the communist period were staying there only for a fixed period and then were leaving for other contracts. In years 1946 to 1991, the migration turnover comprised 2,900,000, while the net migration was only 337 thousand. This was due to the fact that a vast majority of Russian-speaking persons was military personnel with families. Such persons never truly adapted to local conditions, nor learned local language and culture (Katus et al., 2002).

The dissolution of USSR and country's independence in 1991 meant profound changes both for the economy, but also for the ethnic, integration and immigration policy of a re-established Estonian state. First, the industrial sector in which most of Russian-speaking minority worked has suffered the hardest hit during the transformation from communist to free-market economy. This implied that Russian-speaking persons were the biggest losers of Soviet decline, and were at the highest risk of unemployment and socio-economic marginalization. Second, the newly reborn Estonian state and its national elites were afraid of the continuous post-colonial Russian influence on their country internal matters. As the result, the policy adopted towards Russophones was that of a discrimination. Some of Russophones were encouraged and even forced to out-migrate back to Russia – including such categories of workers as military personnel and former KGB (secret policy) officers. Most of Russian-speaking persons in Estonia have been also denied citizenship rights – the proficiency in Estonian is one of a key conditions for applying for Estonian citizenship (see next section for details). Finally, some sectors of the economy including public administration, mass media and education had been reserved for Estonian citizens only. In spite of these measures most of Russophones have remained in Estonia, mostly due to limited economic perspectives in Russia (Hughes, 2005).

When it comes to other migration movements after 1991, the return migration of ethnic Estonians has occurred, but not on a massive scale. At the end of 1980s, approximately 86 thousand Estonians lived in the Western countries (including mostly the UK, the US and Canada), while in the Soviet Union there were ca. 63 thousand. During the first years following re-independence, around 1200-1300 diaspora Estonians have returned to the homeland, those from the West comprising 29% and from Russia and other CIS countries – 71% (Kulu & Tammaru, 2000). In total, for 1990s decade 8 thousand foreign-born persons settled in Estonia, out of which 1500 were ethnic Estonians (Tammur et al., 2016).

Starting from 2000s and more notably from accession into the EU in 2004, the country is experiencing mostly negative migration rate: 40,900 persons immigrated and 69,600 persons left the country between 2000 and 2015. Most of outward migration was directed towards the European Union member states (85%, Tammur et al., 2016), and out of them – mostly towards Finland (ca. 59% of all emigrants, cf. Ministry of Social Affairs, 2014). In the context of immigration, Estonia has one of the largest shares of foreign-born residents in the EU (15%). Yet, most of these foreign-born persons are former internal migrants from Soviet period, originating from ex-Soviet states such as Ukraine, Belarus, Georgia, Kazakhstan and Azerbaijan (Jakobson, 2020). New immigrants come mostly from EU member states (58%), then from countries from post-Soviet bloc (32%) and only 10% from other regions (Tammur et al., 2016).

The evolution of emigration and immigration inflows in contemporary times will be discussed in the following sections of this report. The structure of our report is the following: first we present the methodological approach adopted, define the basic terms and provide an overview of the statistical sources on immigration statistics in Estonia. Then we provide data on immigrant stocks and flows in Estonia, which is complemented by descriptive analysis and critical comments on the reliability of data provided. The final section concludes the report outlining the most important findings, discussing the limitations in statistical evidencing and suggesting puzzles for further research.

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2. Methodology, Definitions and Sources

Methodological approach

Our study relies on a desk research method. In the period of April-August 2020, our research team has gathered data on immigration statistics in Estonia. This report provides a critical analysis of this data, including assessment of data reliability. We extract data from the main statistical sources, including central statistical offices reports, existing surveys and studies and administrative registers. The main focus is on immigration statistics: analysis of migrant flows and stocks. Then, this publicly available data will be compared with the existing estimations on immigrant flows provided by Abel & Cohen (2019).

Definitions of immigrants in Estonian Statistics and evidencing of migrants in statistical registers

According to Statistics Estonia, emigration is defined as “the action by which a person deregisters his or her place of residence from an administrative unit, settlement unit or settlement region of the beginning of the year” and immigration as “the action by which a person registers his or her place of residence in an administrative unit, settlement unit or settlement region other than the one at the beginning of the year” (Statistics Estonia, 2020 a). These definitions were until 2015 – like in Polish case and similarly in other Post-communist economies – based on national registers. In particular, the main source of statistical data on international migration in Estonia was the Population Register of the National Computing Centre. In this sense, a migrant was registered in the PR when one changed the home address. Unfortunately, from year 1992 onwards, the registry of the change of home address was no longer mandatory for Estonian citizens. Consequently, data on out-migration from Estonia coming from the PR did not capture all international migration episodes of Estonians, as many of them wanted to keep some ties with their home country and did not deregister (Tammur et al., 2016). The very rough estimate based on previous research suggests that ca. half of the changes in address in Estonia was being registered. The second source of data, especially on return migration was the Remigration Department of the Estonian Citizenship and Migration board (CMB). This register was mostly helpful for ethnic Estonians from Eastern Europe, who usually did not have Estonian citizenship and have to register at CMB to start applying procedure. Yet, the returnees from Western countries who usually had Estonian citizenship usually did not register in this database (Kulu & Tammaru, 2000). Summing up: until 2015, like in the case of other Central and Eastern European countries, the statistics on international migration, especially the one on out-migration is not perfect and most of flows are usually underestimated. Finally, we should mention that the older data from communist period, especially the censuses based on Soviet methodology (carried in 1959, 1970, 1979 and 1989) are also imperfect, moreover the information on country of birth was not included (Katus et al., 2002).

In 2015 Statistic Estonia has adopted a completely new methodology for evidencing migration. Instead of a register which includes migration events, the person is believed to stay in Estonia if given procedures are performed in all administrative registers – the so-called ‘signs of life’ procedure. On the other hand, when such procedures are not performed in connection with a person evidenced in Estonian administrative register – this person is considered as a migrant who has left Estonia. Consequently, from 2015 the data on immigration and emigration in Estonia is much more reliable, but it cannot be compared to data from previous periods (Tammur et al., 2016). (Eurostat 2017).

Picture: Payam Moin Afshari/Unsplash.com

3. Estonian diaspora

The Estonian diaspora has been formed by three consecutive waves of emigration described in the introduction: first started in late 19th Century and continued to 1st World War, second occurring mostly during the World War 2nd, and the third one started in the late 1980s and continued until now. Traditionally researchers divide the communities of Estonians living abroad into 2 major groups: Eastern and Western sub-diasporas (Tammaru et al., 2010). According to OECD statistics, in 2010 the total emigrant population of Estonia was estimated at 143.5 thousand and it was slightly feminized: 80.8 thousand immigrant women versus 62.7 thousand males (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Most important destinations for Estonian diaspora (2010)

As for 2010, still the biggest number of Estonians lived in Russian Federation – 56.3 thousand persons, followed by new important destination – Finland (22 thousand). It is important to mention here that the Estonian citizenship is based on the principle of 'state continuity'. After regaining the independence, Estonians have introduced the constitution in 1992 which re-established the pre-Soviet Estonian republic, and consequently – its 1938 law on citizenship. According to these regulations, the right to Estonian citizenship was granted to all citizens and their descendants from pre-1940 period. In such a case, many Russian-speaking internal migrants from Soviet period were deprived of a right to apply for Estonian citizenship, while many Estonian diasporans still living in Post-Soviet Eastern republics still retained such rights. Currently, the Estonian citizenship is granted by birth from Estonian parent(s) or by naturalization. Yet, in the case of naturalization the person who applies has to reside legally at least 8 years in Estonian territory and pass the Estonian language proficiency examination and pass the exam on the knowledge of Estonian constitution. Additionally, persons who have citizenship of another country have to renounce it, as double or multiple citizenships are not allowed (Hughes, 2005). Consequently, most of the Russian-speaking population of Estonia, most of which either arrived from other Soviet republics in 1945-1989 period or they parents did so, are either stateless or with the citizenship of their country of birth (Saar, 2020).

After 2010, the most important destination for Estonian migration is Finland due to geographical and cultural proximity (Finnish language is related to Estonian) and the higher pay on Finnish labor market. For instance, in 2012, 38% of migrants below 35 years went to Finland, while for the 35+ category this was 54% (Masso et al., 2016). Most of migrants who leave to Finland are males and on average with lower education attainment than the average in Estonia. Many of them actually are cross-border commuters: their families stay in Estonia, while they work in Finland and other Nordic countries (Sweden, Norway) and make occasional visits in the home country every month. Although Estonia has not developed a complex diaspora policy, it has created some instruments to enable mostly socio-cultural reintegration of returnees and their families, as many of them do not speak Estonian language (Saar, 2020).

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Picture: Serhat Beyazkaya/Unsplash.com

4. Immigrant stocks in Estonia

The last general population (and housing) census in Estonia had been conducted in 2011¹. Based on the census and other ongoing studies, Statistics Estonia – the governmental institution responsible for data operation – gathers data on migration. According to this database in 2020 the foreign-origin population constituted for 28% of the total population (365 464 out of 1 328 976 persons, Figure 2)². Compared to previous years the percentage of foreign-origin population slightly increased (27% in three previous consecutive years). The first generation (i.e. foreign-born persons) is still numerous, accounting for almost half of the total foreign-origin population (49%).

Figure 2. Native and foreign-origin population in Estonia (2020)

Source: Statistics Estonia, latest update: 2020/09/30

A further disaggregation of the above-mentioned data in recent years shows that the biggest group amongst foreign-origin population in Estonia consists of females aged 60-64 years old (Figure 3). This suggests that foreign-origin population is predominantly old and dominated by the ex-internal migrants from Soviet Union.

¹ <https://www.stat.ee/en/statistics-estonia/population-census-2021/2011-population-and-housing-census> [access: 16.02.2021]

² RV071: NATIVE AND FOREIGN-ORIGIN POPULATION, 1 JANUARY by Year, Native / foreign-origin population, Sex and Age group. Please note that foreign-origin population is a peculiar term for Estonian statistics, as many of foreigners are stateless, but were born on Estonian territory and have non-Estonian parents.

Figure 3. Native and foreign-origin population in Estonia (2020)

Source: Statistics Estonia, latest update: 2020/09/30

An understandable observation can be made of the total number of persons under 20 years amongst foreign-origin population being significantly lower than in the native population. Interestingly, the proportion of women in their late working age (55-70 years) in the foreign-origin population visibly outnumbers the younger female population (30-54 years). However, when it comes to the native population this proportion is reversed (Figure 4).

Figure 4. The age and gender structure of the native population

Source: Statistics Estonia, latest update: 2020/09/30

Another way of identifying persons with a migration background in the population census is the analysis of the dataset on the country of birth or the country of citizenship. According to the former, 200 417 persons living in Estonia in 2020 did not hold the country's citizenship (15% of the total population), and almost identical proportion concerns the data on the country of birth. As illustrated by the chart below, the vast majority of the non-Estonian citizenship refers to the so-called third countries (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Country of citizenship of foreign-origin population in Estonia (2020)

Source: Statistics Estonia, latest update: 2020/09/30

Whereas the data on the country of citizenship and the one on the country of birth regarding Estonian population are almost identical, it seems more useful to refer to the data on the country of birth when analysing a more detailed structure of migration population. It is worth noting that the two datasets slightly differ, but the dominant trends for Estonian population remain the same. The dominant non-Estonian country of birth in 2020 was Russian (Figure 6), accounting for 66% amongst the total number, and followed by Ukraine (14%) and Belarus (6%). The dominance of Russia as the country of birth amongst foreign-born in Estonia can be a result of long-lasting historical, geopolitical and economic ties between those two countries as described in the introduction. The immigration of Ukrainians to Estonia has increased after the political crisis in Eastern Ukraine since 2015 and the reasons for this increase are similar to all CEE countries (better salaries, geographic proximity, relatively low costs of living, popularity of Russian language, established during and after the Soviet era migration nets).

Figure 6. Foreign-origin population in Estonia by country of birth (%), 2020

Source: Statistics Estonia, latest update: 2020/05/12

According to the data on the country of birth, the number of non-Estonians living in Estonia varies considerably regarding the age structure (Figure 7). Compared to the population pyramids of foreign-origin persons in Estonia and contrary to the conclusions drawn from them, no significantly dominant group can be seen.

Figure 7. The age structure of non-Estonians living in Estonia (2020)

Source: Statistics Estonia, latest update: 2020/05/12

When looking closer at the dynamic of the migration stocks in Estonia in recent years, a growing trend of the total foreign-origin population can be observed since 2017, with its peak in 2019 (368 thousand persons).

Figure 8. Stock of foreign-origin population by year

Source: Statistics Estonia, latest update: 2020/05/12

Nevertheless, the composition of respective countries has not changed in any visible way. The Russian origin should be distinguished, consequently dominating in the last years (ca. 120 thousand persons), followed by Ukrainian and Belarussian origin (the latter two not exceeding 30 thousand persons).

Figure 9. Foreign-origin population in Estonia by country of birth

Source: Statistics Estonia, latest update: 2020/05/12

The data of Statistics Estonia on foreign-origin population shows a decreasing trend until 2015, declining from 365 thousand persons in 2012 to 350 thousand in 2015 (Figure 10). Please note that in 2015 the method of registering immigration in Estonia has changed, thus data from 2016 onwards (Figure 8) cannot be compared to data from period until 2015.

Figure 10. Foreign-origin population in Estonia

Source: Statistics Estonia, latest update: 2020/05/12

Picture: Roman Wimmers/Unsplash.com

5. Immigrant flows in Estonia

Estonia has followed a very similar pattern of migration transition as many other countries of Central and Eastern Europe such as Poland, Czech Republic, Hungary, Slovakia and Slovenia. In the 2000s, following the EU accession Estonia continued to be a mostly emigration country, and Estonians left country for such destinations as Ireland, the UK, Finland, Norway, Sweden and Germany (Włodarska-Frykowska, 2017). Also in the first years of 2010s, the emigration flows from the country has outnumbered immigration flows. As discussed earlier, the official statistics for emigration of Estonians until 2015 are definitely underestimated, as deregistering from Population Register was not mandatory. Moreover, many of Estonians adopted a strategy of circular migration to Finland, moving back to their families who remained in the homeland every month or even on weekends.

Figure 11. Emigration and immigration flows in Estonia per year
Source: Eurostat (2021).

As the result of this migration wave after 2004, Finland (52 thousand persons) has surpassed Russia (18 thousand) as the most important destination country for Estonians as for 2020 (see Figure 1 as for situation in 2010), followed by the UK (9.3 thousand), Germany (5.7 thousand), Sweden (4.6 thousand) and the US (4.3 thousand, Figure 12).

Figure 12. Number of Estonians residing abroad by destination (2020)
 Source: Statistics Estonia, latest update: 2020/05/12

Nevertheless, as in the case of the other countries of the region Estonia has been recently transformed into a net immigration country: this trend was already visible in 2014, before Estonia changed the methodology of evidencing immigration and emigration in their population registers ('signs of life' method, as discussed in previous section). Obviously, the high increase of both emigration and immigration flows in 2015 is associated with the change of methodology which from now on better captures real magnitude of flows. Yet, already in 2015 Estonia has received more immigrants than emigrants left the country (Figure 11). This change was associated with an important change in migration policy: until 2016 there was a quota imposed on the number of residence permits for foreigners. Moreover, the foreign workers employed in Estonia had to be paid at least the national average salary, to downward pressure on wages of low-skilled Estonians. Yet, in 2016 Estonia has simplified temporary access to its labour market to foreigners from third countries who hold visa, provided they register their short-term employment with Police and Border Guard. Since 2018, the third country nationals can work in Estonia for a period of 1 year when holding a special D-visa. Moreover, in 2017 Estonia has also introduced a law enabling the entry of labour migrants for seasonal employment in selected sectors such as agriculture or hospitality (Jakobson & Kalev, 2020). All of these reforms resulted in a rapid inflow of immigrants, reaching historical high – 18.2 thousand persons in 2019. It must be stressed that these numbers do not reflect all the migration movements, as in this year in total over 60 thousand documents for immigrants were issued, including 2218 first residence permits for employment, 25672 D-visas and 32245 short-term labour registrations (Jakobson & Kalev, 2020, Figure 13).

Figure 13. Short-term immigration to Estonia by type of documents issued
 Source: Jakobson & Kalev, 2020.

The turning point in migration transition mentioned earlier is also clearly visible while looking at the table presenting immigrant population by country and birth in the last 15 years (Figure 14), with the share of Ukrainian immigration rising drastically after the year 2015. Most of the short-term migrants who work in Estonia actually come from this country, and their inflow started with the war in Donbas and political crisis in 2015.

Figure 14. Immigrants in Estonia by country of birth
 Source: Statistics Estonia, latest update: 2020/05/12

When it comes to assessment of the reliability of estimates of Abel and Cohen (2019) with Statistics Estonia, the magnitude of flows in 5-years period seems to be quite accurate, but there is a discrepancy in terms of bilateral flows: especially the number of migrants leaving Estonia for most important destination – Finland – is greatly underestimated.

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Picture: Rach Teo/Unsplash.com

6. Migration narrative scenario for Estonia

In this subchapter we focus on the migration potential of Estonia as a sending and a host country, taking into account the important push and pull factors such as the demographic structure, economy, social attitudes towards immigrants and Russian minority and political realm. As such, these scenario narratives do not aim to foresee the migration future of Estonia but rather outline the possible directions in which demographic processes can develop, with regard to international migration.

6.1 Factors influencing the situation of immigrants in Estonia

The first point to discuss is demography. The population number in Estonia fluctuates around 1.3 million and tends to rise year to year, despite the time of the Covid-19 pandemic. For instance, in 2018 the figures of residents in Estonia equated to 1.319 million, in 2019 – 1.324 million, in 2020 – 1.328 million and in 2021 – 1.330 million (Eurostat, 2022 a). As explained by Statistics Estonia, immigration is distinctly driving population growth in the country. In other words, due to immigration events, instead of expected population decline, the population of Estonia has increased (Statistics Estonia, 2020 b).

Regarding economic indicators, Estonia has one of the lowest unemployment rates in the EU27, which in 2021 amounted to 5% (OECD, 2021 a). The structure of GDP, and hiring by sector, indicate that the Estonian economy can be perceived as a developed one. In 2020, agriculture constituted 2% of the annual gross domestic product, industry – 23% and services – 76%. On the other hand, in 2019 agriculture hired 3.1% of the working-age population, industry 28.7% and services – 68.1% (OECD, 2021 b; OECD, 2021 c; OECD, 2021 d).

Regarding economic indicators, Estonia has one of the lowest unemployment rates in the EU27, which in 2021 amounted to 5%

Stability in the political scene is crucial for increasing the migration influx. According to the Centre for Eastern Studies, Eurosceptical and populist parties appeared in the country's political scene. In January 2021 the new coalition government has been established, which consisted of centrists and reformists on par with nationalists and anti-EU Conservative People's Party (EKRE) and The Fatherland Party (Hyndle-Hussein, 2021 a). Taking into account the local elections conducted in October 2021, the EKRE party doubled its result in comparison to the previous elections (a rise from 6.7% to 13.2%). It is estimated that this effect could be higher if some Russian-speaking minority members decided to vote. The group is opposing the EU membership of Estonia and the energetic transformation of the country (Hyndle-Hussein, 2021 b). Considering the popularity of the Eurosceptic opinions among the Estonians and Russian minority and imperial politics of Russia, we may presume that in the following three decades Estonia may be a host country of Russian citizens, instead of the EU ones.

We need to mention the Estonian-Russian relation on the national level, as the perception of the minorities in a given country influences the situation of potential immigrants. The history of the Russian community in Estonia began during the communist era when USSR citizens migrated there as an industry, military or administration workers. After the collapse of the Soviet Union, Russians did not acquire Estonian citizenship, instead became stateless (Minority Rights Group, 2015). In 2015, the citizenship act facilitating the citizenship granting for children up to 15 years old and seniors above 65 years old, have been introduced. The other groups have been granted a so-called 'non-citizen passport' allowing them to have the Estonian passport after passing the B2-level Estonian language exam (Hyndle-Hussein, 2015). Therefore, the inequality between both national groups can influence the situation of the Russian immigrants in Estonia.

6.2 Migration prospect

Estonia is a host country for five nations: Germans, British, Finnish, Ukrainians and Russians. Interestingly, in the statistics also appears a large share of immigrants from the category 'country unknown'.

When it comes to the migrant networks in Estonia, the largest group consists of persons falling in the category of 'unknown countries' which in 2020 equated to slightly over 5,3 thousand (Statistics Estonia, 2021). This group is being counted since 2015 when totalled 9,5 thousand (Ibidem). The numbers reached the peak in 2017 amounting to 11 thousand, and in the following years slowly decreased to fluctuate around 5 thousand persons. We cannot presume the future of this group as we do not have the exact data on country of origin or country of birth.

The next largest migrant network in Estonia consists of citizens of Russia, whose numbers in 2011 equated to 1,2 thousand, in 2016 – ca. 650 persons and in 2020 – 1,1 thousand (Statistics Estonia, 2021). Immigrants from Russia are received unfavourably in Estonia because of its Soviet history, during which Russians arrived mostly as military, administrative or industry workers and dominated the social and political realms of the state. After the collapse of the USSR, the division between Estonian and Russian communities still appeared visible, which manifested e.g. in the use of Russian or Estonian language as the main part of national identity and attending to separate schools.

In 2020, the Russian minority constituted 30 % of the residents in Estonia (Mägi et al., 2020) The common perception of Russian immigrants overlaps with the one of the Russian minority. Therefore, the access to the Estonian labour market by the Russian immigrants can be limited by the Russophobia and general reluctance toward this group stemming from historical experiences. The future of Russian immigrants in Estonia is not clear. On the one hand, the network size can diminish due to exclusion from the national labour market. On the other, it can increase due to the imperial politics of Russia and the mobilisation of the Russian minorities abroad.

Another important migrant network consists of Ukrainians, whose figures show the tendency of growing. For instance, the number of them in 2011 was ca. 270 persons, in 2015 – nearly 700 and in 2020, despite the fact of the pandemic, the number equated to 2,1 thousand (Statistics Estonia, 2021). The influx of Ukrainians to Estonia partly stems from the conflict in Ukraine. Taking into account Russian imperial politics and the fact of granting Ukrainians refugee status by the Estonian law (Ministry of the Interior, 2015), we may presume that this community may grow during the following thirty years.

Finnish people and the representation of Finland view play a significant role in self-perception by the Estonians. The number of immigrants from Finland in the last decade oscillated between 500 and 3 thousand persons, with its peak in 2019 (Statistics Estonia, 2021). The high share of newcomers from Finland can partly result from the return migration, as Estonian citizens eagerly emigrate to Finland. Therefore, we cannot explicitly indicate the traits of the Finnish network in Estonia as Statistics Estonia gather data on immigrants by the previous country of residence, not the country of birth.

The last two groups of immigrants in Estonia come from the United Kingdom and Germany. When it comes to the British, the size of this community tends to grow as in 2011 was ca. 120 persons, in 2015 - ca. 340 persons and in 2020 – nearly over 610 persons (Statistics Estonia, 2021). Considering the fact that the figures did not decrease due to the pandemic, we may assume that the British citizens arrive in Estonia mostly as highly qualified employees with international contracts. The size of the German network in Estonia did not exceed 150 persons until 2018 when it amounted to 500 persons. Due to the pandemic in 2020, the figures totalled roughly 400 persons. On this basis, we can presume that Germans, similarly to British, are hired as international employees and their immigration is dependent on the global economic situation.

Picture: Mark Zu/Unsplash.com

7. Conclusions: Covid-19 pandemic: possible effects on immigration

The dynamic transformation of Estonia into an important net-receiving/immigration country was put abruptly to a halt by Covid-19 pandemic. Estonia reacted very quickly, declaring emergency situation already on March 12, 2020. The border controls have been reinstalled and government stopped issuing visas to third country nationals. Third country nationals who were already legally staying in the country could have their visa or residence permit extended up to 31 August 2020. Estonia has kept the borders closed to new migrants for the summer 2020, in spite of the protests of many employers, including mostly agricultural entrepreneurs. After a period of negotiations in the government, new laws on seasonal migration were put into practice, imposing the obligations of 14-day period isolation for newly arrived immigrants before they can assume work and the reduction of the time limit of seasonal work from 9 to 6 months a year. This is because the anti-immigrant Conservative People's Party of Estonia (EKRE) has entered the government coalition and perceives Covid-19 pandemic to change the migration policy of the country into more restrictive, giving preference to encouragement of return for Estonians residing abroad (Jakobson & Kalev, 2020).

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